

Taming the Swarm: a role-based approach for autonomous agents

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Abstract. Hyper-distributed applications leverage the Compute Continuum to offer highly-available, trustworthy and secure services with low latency. Given the number of managed devices and their heterogeneity, finding an optimal distribution of these application’s functionalities is a challenging problem tackled either manually or with a resource-hungry, centralised solution. This work proposes a ground-breaking programming environment where applications are composed of several cooperative roles to be played by the devices. A novel software stack transforms each device into an Autonomous ageNT (ANT) deciding which roles it executes, according to its capabilities and context, and enabling the construction of a cooperative, self-organized platform.

Keywords: swarm · edge · cloud · compute continuum · distributed system · programming model · decentralized · platform · autonomous agent

1 Introduction

With the advance of Cloud Computing, distributed applications have evolved and become ubiquitous. Although most of the data is being collected by IoT devices, 80% of its processing still occurs in data centres and centralised computing facilities [6]. The Cloud Computing paradigm strongly relies on the network infrastructure, which incurs high communication latency and significant energy consumption overheads while leaving the computing resources embedded in the devices at the Edge of the network under-utilised. Abusing the Cloud hinders the progress towards becoming a climate-neutral and sustainable society.

Hyper-distributed applications, which assemble data and resources from several multi-tenant, geographically distributed infrastructures connected through uneven networks – often with an increased probability of network disruption –, require low latencies for being offered with high availability, trust and security [2]. The Compute Continuum solves these challenges by combining the Edge and Cloud into a single computing platform [9], leveraging the capacities of the IoT, Edge and Far-Edge devices, and reducing dependency on the Cloud and network. This unified platform increases IT systems’ responsiveness, accuracy,

and energy efficiency. Defining and deploying applications in devices across the Continuum while reducing human interaction becomes an open question.

Swarms are a novel architecture targeting the Compute Continuum where multiple autonomous agents cooperate in a fully decentralised manner to reach a global objective. The work presented in this article embraces this paradigm shift and introduces COLMENA: an open platform for large, heterogeneous, and dynamic groups of devices across the Continuum integrating their capabilities – compute, store, connectivity, and cyber-physical – with seamless management across providers, connectivity types and network zones. Each component of the infrastructure (hardware node, virtual environment, or even a whole virtualization platform) becomes an Autonomous agent (ANT) aware of its capabilities and context; ANTs self-organize to establish an agile, secure and fully decentralized platform with a mesh architecture that enables collaboration through inter-device communication, data sharing and computation exchange.

To ease the development, deployment, operation and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications targeting this platform, we provide a programming model that describes the application’s logic as a composite of roles defined by their behaviour (program logic) and a set of hardware requirements. Each ANT hosts a light-weight, energy-efficient software platform that collaboratively drives the actual distribution of roles by autonomously selecting the roles executed by the ANT according to its capabilities, its current context, the requirements of the roles and application-specific indicators for the expected levels of performance, energy consumption and the quality of service (QoS) and experience (QoE) and those currently being delivered. This decision-making autonomy opposes resource-greedy, centralised management mechanisms and paves the way to extreme-scale elastic, heterogeneous systems. It enhances the robustness and efficiency of applications with the flexibility to quickly react to infrastructure or workload changes by dynamically reassigning the roles played by each ANT with zero setup and reconfiguration effort.

Such a programming environment contributes to the definition of next-generation computing and data technologies by easing the programming, deployment and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications on the Continuum. To enhance the trust of end-users in these systems, COLMENA aims at keeping a transparent and comprehensible operation open to the adoption of new generations of hardware (processors, network or smart systems) that make the infrastructure better and, thus, improve the interoperability of the system and avoid vendor lock-in. Besides, to secure access to data and smart systems, the framework incorporates encryption, authentication, and authorization mechanisms that guarantee the privacy of the end-users.

The article continues by analyzing previous work in related knowledge fields. Section 3 introduces the fundamental concepts on which the solution builds and details the software stack supporting the framework and its programming model. The last section concludes the article and identifies future lines of research.

2 Related Work

The orchestration of services in the Cloud is often achieved through the use of Cloud Operating Systems (OS) that manage the creation of (multi-)cloud environments, as well as the deployment and operation of services as compositions of virtualised entities. Vendor-proprietary solutions are the most well-known examples (Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform, and Microsoft Azure). Still, there are also open-source, interoperable solutions such as OpenStack and OpenNebula. Due to its popularity, Kubernetes (K8s) is a widespread solution supported by most Cloud OSs, to orchestrate containers in clusters. To the best of our knowledge, all these solutions manage the infrastructure and the virtual environments centrally. The Edge presents a heterogeneous scenario with constrained resources and unstable networking. Some lightweight implementations of Kubernetes (e.g., K3s) focus on the resource constraints issue. Frameworks like Cilium and clusterlink provide networking and security functionalities to Kubernetes edge clusters. However, the Edge demands a decentralised management solution for not staying a surrogate of the Cloud.

Developing services deployed across the continuum is based on tailored solutions where data is collected (and often pre-processed) on the Edge and then sent to the cloud for archiving or analysis using publish-subscribe standards (e.g., MQTT), Apache Kafka or Remote Procedure Call (RPC) for synchronous communication. Data management systems proposed for IoT [1]¹, support the fast ingestion and analysis of time series in the Cloud, requiring continuous data transfers to and from edge devices, thus disabling fast responses and the flexibility required by swarms. Other solutions [18]² focus on resource heterogeneity and restrictions, and on avoiding data transfers to and from the Cloud but assume fixed infrastructures. The fully decentralized nature of Swarm requires new approaches for managing and processing data. For instance, dataClay [15] is an object-based data storage solution optimized for dynamic environments.

Another way of defining distributed applications in the Continuum is by using programming models. Traditional programming models for distributed systems – e.g., data analytics frameworks [7, 19] and general-purpose workflow managers [8, 14], – have centralized global orchestrators. Another common paradigm for developing concurrent and distributed systems is the actor model, where an application can be defined as a composition of standalone actors communicating among them. Erlang and Akka implement the actor model, but their runtimes are not prepared to face the challenges set by the continuum. Programming models targeting swarms – e.g., Buzz [16] – have focused on designing simple reactive controllers, neural networks, state machines, or behaviour trees for individual devices that give rise to desired swarm behaviours [3, 11, 13]. Mandrake [5] proposes a programming model to define decentralized applications that deal with autonomous agents built on Protocols Over Things [17]. However, unlike COLMENA, Mandrake and Buzz have not been applied to the Continuum nor

¹ BWorld Robot Control Software. <https://www.influxdata.com>

² ExtremeDB <https://www.mcobject.com/extremedbfamily>

considered the dynamic allocation of roles on autonomous devices. In the literature, role assignment in multi-agent systems (allocation of items between different entities) is typically solved in a centralized manner by running classical optimization algorithms [4, 10, 12], and there are attempts for a distributed allocation are market-based and built on contract net protocol. Discovering controllers for individuals that result in desired emergent properties at a collective level is notoriously difficult.

COLMENA is a novel approach to develop and orchestrate services across the Continuum. On the one hand, the decomposition of the service into several roles extends the actor model adapting it to the Compute Continuum by enabling the scaling of the number of instances of each role. On the other hand, COLMENA proposes a novel mechanism for orchestration where devices autonomously decide the role assignments based on QoS metrics. A myriad of frameworks measure different metrics – e.g., Scaphandre for energy consumption –, extract and standardise them – e.g., OpenTelemetry – and aggregate them for archival or real-time analysis – Prometheus.

3 The COLMENA framework

COLMENA aims to support all stakeholders related to hyper-distributed applications; hence, it considers all the stages of their lifecycle: construction, deployment, and operation. At construction time, it aims at easing the coding to the Developers. At deployment time, it helps Providers to instantiate the service on an infrastructure belonging to one or several Infrastructure Owners. At operation time, it aspires to provide Infrastructure Owners with control over their devices, Providers with mechanisms to monitor and control the application behaviour, including continuous software updates brought by Maintainers, and End-Users with an extremely secure, available and reliable solution to their needs.

To achieve that, COLMENA constructs a platform assembling a large heterogeneous set of IoT devices and smart systems, edge servers and cloud platforms composing the Compute Continuum. Successful examples of very large organisations comprising heterogeneous individuals are organic colonies in which each member autonomously decides how it contributes to the community by playing specific roles in their societies according to its skills and context. Likewise, devices composing an IT infrastructure become Autonomous AgeNTs (ANTs) that, according to their capabilities and current context, decide how they deliver value to the whole organisation. ANTs self-organise to compose a mesh architecture that enables communication among peers, establishes data-sharing mechanisms, and allows the exchange of serverless computation. In this simile, developing a service running on such a platform resembles describing the shape of the society formed by the individuals; i.e., describing the roles/functionalities in the system indicating their associated behaviour and the necessary skills/capabilities to perform it (software and hardware).

Finding an optimal distribution of the functionalities across the continuum is one of the current challenges of hyper-distributed services deployment. The

solver needs to consider a very large infrastructure, the system’s heterogeneity increases the complexity of the problem, and the dynamism of the networks and the variability of workload impedes eliciting and applying general rules to simplify the problem and forces a continuous evaluation and re-adaptation. Currently, services are deployed following a static – often, sub-optimal – strategy or using a resource-hungry centralised solution. Instead, we propose to build on the autonomy of the devices and give them the freedom to fail. Each ANT autonomously selects which functionalities/roles are the best fit to carry out depending on the current needs of the services. For individuals to evaluate their performance when running a role or the overall quality of the service (QoE and QoS) being delivered, it is necessary to establish a set of key indicators and their expected values. Through these indicators, each device can realize the needs and excesses of each specific functionality and, then, act accordingly considering its current context and individual performance selecting the best-fitting roles for itself to contribute to an optimal distribution.

3.1 Software Stack

To build such a platform and operate services on it, we propose a four-layer software – depicted in Figure 1 – where its base (layer 0) are the **IT resources** composing the target infrastructure. These can be either individual hardware nodes – e.g., single board computers, edge servers, robots –, virtual instances – virtual machines and containers – or whole virtualisation platforms – Clouds and Container-as-a-Service clusters like K8s or K3s. These components can present a wide range of heterogeneity regarding the available network interfaces, computing devices, smart systems (both, sensors and actuators), and storage devices.

The first software layer, **ANT Handler**, converts each IT device into an interoperable ANT while ensuring efficiency by optimising the operation to the specific compute, network, storage and sensing/actuating capabilities of the ANT and the current circumstances. Information about the capabilities of the ANT and their usage is collected by the *ANT Monitor*. Pursuing better resource exploitation, higher performance and lower energy consumption, the *Role Optimiser* customises the software of the roles adapting it to the specific computing devices, the *Communication Controller* considers the current network conditions to establish communication channels under specific requirements (e.g., latency, bandwidth), and the *Smart System Controller* provides a generic interface to interact securely and remotely with the embedded sensors and actuators. For Infrastructure Owners to restrict the software to run on the device, the access to its smart systems, the amount of shared computational and storage resources and its electric power consumption, the layer provides the *ANT Configuration Manager* tool. All the components within this layer are deployed on every ANT operating on the host device without interaction with other ANTs.

The second layer establishes a collaboration plane among ANTs presenting the infrastructure to the upper layers as a **Swarm Platform** rather than a collection of heterogeneous devices. All its components run in all ANTs; however, they cooperate with the instances of the same component in other ANTs to

Fig. 1: COLMENA project software stack

achieve their purpose. The *Context Manager* provides ANTs with awareness of their self-context – capacities (leveraging the ANT Monitor), identity, location and ownership – and social context – neighbouring devices capabilities, proximity, volatility and trustworthiness. The *Sharing Manager* establishes mechanisms to interact with the platform to publish software, share data and operate on it seamlessly across the continuum. The *Distributed Service Manager* selects which roles are hosted locally aiming to contribute to the overall service performance. Internally, it elaborates a QoE & QoS Assessment report that is fed into an AI model, enhanced with learning techniques, to determine the number of instances of each role to be played by the device considering its current conditions and owner preferences. Continuously reconsidering this decision allows a dynamic adaptation of the deployment delivering an agile, robust and efficient platform.

The purpose of the **Service Tools** layer is to offer tools that support service stakeholders relying on the Swarm; hence, they do not necessarily run on an ANT of the system but on devices with access to the platform. Three tools aid Service Developers (SD) by easing the implementation and maintenance of the service. The *Swarm Programming Model* allows the description of a service as a composite of different roles indicating their requirements and establishing their KPIs. *Role Operation Abstractions* simplify the development of role behaviours by providing generic interfaces to communicate, share data, interact with smart systems, and distribute the computational load of the role. Finally, the layer offers the Swarm Intelligence library implementing continuous learning and Swarm Intelligence algorithms to ease the development of intelligent ser-

Fig. 2: COLMENA Deployment model

vices. At the end of the construction phase, SDs deliver a software bundle to Service Providers (SP) who, through the *Service Deployment Tool*, instantiate the service propagating its information and software images across the platform. At service operation time, SPs can monitor and control the deployed services through the *Service Operation Dashboard*; this tool also allows the application of software updates enabling a CI/CD methodology for the software development.

Services relying on the platform to offer solutions with extremely high availability, reliability and trustworthiness to End-Users are at the top of this stack.

COLMENA leverages virtualized environments and uses containerization solutions like Docker or Balena for securing its service executions and facilitating software management. Figure 2 depicts how the components of the software stack are deployed. Each ANT hosts the execution of one container, known as the COLMENA Agent, hosting the two lowest layers of the architecture for handling the underlying resources, providing efficient performance and supporting all the collaboration mechanisms. Roles are executed as individual containers containing the logic of their behaviour and the Role Operation Abstractions.

3.2 Programming Model

COLMENA provides a programming model that eases the development of services by decomposing them into a set of roles that ANTs autonomously decide whether to play or not according to their current contextual circumstances. The significant circumstances, either static (e.g., device ownership) or dynamic (e.g., location in the case of mobile devices), are specific for each service. For example, a service could require being in a given city, more service-specific information such as the location within the company premises, or a combination of both. Instead of supporting only a set of predefined circumstances, COLMENA allows custom contexts by extending the `Context` class. Its attribute `structure` defines a complete taxonomy of a contextual aspect (e.g., Building-Floor-Room) and the `locate` method returns the current classification of the device using basic information collected from sensors and the device configuration.

The roles of a service do not work in isolation; instances of a role and different roles can cooperate. To simplify this cooperation, COLMENA offers two mechanisms: `Channels`, for messages passing during the operation of the roles, and `Data`, for creating shared data spaces. Developers can limit the scope of cooperation using the context taxonomies; for instance, using the company premises taxonomy, a service could require establishing a different shared data space for each floor or a communication channel to communicate devices in the same room. For implementing a new service, application developers extend the `Service` class and add decorators to its constructor indicating for each Context taxonomy (`@Context`) its name and implementing class, and for each cooperation mechanism (`@Data` and `@Channel`) its name and scope.

Roles within the service are defined as inner classes and extend the `Role` class. By decorating its constructor with `@Data` and `@Channel`, developers indicate the cooperation elements necessary to achieve its purpose. The COLMENA platform transparently ensures that channels and data values are appropriately shared with other ANTs according to the current context of the host. The logic supporting the role is implemented by overriding the `behavior` method. COLMENA considers two types of roles: persistent and asynchronous. The former ones require decorating the `behavior` method with `@Persistent` and the method is invoked permanently to run the same logic (e.g., getting an image from a camera and publishing it). The latter react to a message reception and their method is executed on an event basis (e.g., processing a published image). Their `behavior` method is decorated with `@Async` indicating the channel on which a reception will trigger the method execution passing the message as a parameter.

Some role purposes are bound to specific circumstances of the host; for instance, a role for controlling people entering any of the buildings of the company should be running on devices located at all the lobbies of the buildings regardless of the floor. Decorating the constructor of the role with `@Context`, developers restrict the devices playing the role to those that currently match some classification in a specific taxonomy. Likewise, role implementations may require specific hardware to run; with the `@Requirements` decorator, developers indicate the hardware requirements to host it.

Developers specify the indicators that drive the instantiation of a role by decorating its constructor with `@KPI` setting a condition that determines the necessity of running it. Conditions use metrics that are collected dynamically at execution time. As with the contextual circumstances, COLMENA provides some predefined metrics (e.g., the number of players of a role). However, some metrics are application-specific and their value is explicitly handled by roles decorated with `@Metric` indicating the metric name. Since the KPIs for two different roles can use the same metric but with a different scope, the scope and timeframe to consider are indicated in the condition following pattern `MetricName(ContextName=scope)[time]`. Listing 1.1 implements two complementary roles for a video surveillance application using the examples set in the section.

```

class Sensor(Role):
    @Requirements("/devices/camera")
    @Context(name="premises",
            scope="*.*.lobby")
    @Channel(name="pending")
    @Metric(name="sensed")
    @KPI("num_players(Sensor, $ME)=1")
    def __init__(self, *arg, **kwarg):
        # Initialize the role

    @Persistent()
    def behavior(self):
        image = # Get image from camera
        self.pending.publish(image)
        self.sensed.publish(1)

class Processor(Role):
    @Requirements("/processor/GPU")
    @Data(name="arrival_log")
    @Channel(name="pending")
    @KPI(processed({ME})[5s] > 1)
    def __init__(self, *arg, **kwarg):
        # Initialize the role

    @Async(message="pending")
    def behavior(self, message):
        result = process_image(message)
        self.arrival_log.add(result)
        self.arrival_log.publish()

    def process_image(self, image):
        # Call Computer Vision Library

```

(a) Sensor role

(b) Processor role

Listing 1.1: Roles for a video surveillance use case

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This manuscript introduces COLMENA, a framework for developing, deploying, and operating hyper-distributed applications across the Compute Continuum. The framework models these applications as a composition of interacting roles (or functionalities) and, through the proposed software stack, it converts each device into an autonomous agent aware of its capabilities and current context. The framework also provides communication and shared data abstractions that enable cooperation among roles (and devices). Unlike other existing solutions, which base their orchestration on centralised engines or consensus, COLMENA proposes a ground-breaking approach based on the freedom to fail; devices autonomously pick the roles to run considering the current and desired levels for some key indicators related to the overall Quality of Service/Experience, the performance of the role or application-specific conditions.

To achieve a fully decentralized platform, we will build on peer-to-peer solutions for message passing, data management and compute sharing. Regarding the implementation of the role selection, we consider mixing different approaches depending on the capacities of each device. Resource-constrained devices could leverage heuristic-based solutions; however, we will investigate combining AI-based approaches, such as reinforcement learning, with economic models such as game theory or auctions for larger devices. We will also incorporate privacy and security mechanisms for authentication, authorization, and accounting.

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